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Application of Transcendental Meditation Using a Smartphone Meditation App to Improve Class Discipline

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Research suggests that contemplative practices like meditation and relaxation techniques have an array of benefits, including self-awareness and self-regulatory skills, better learning outcomes, and alleviating learning anxiety. Increasingly, these practices are being adapted in educational settings to foster the development of key self-regulatory skills required for improved class discipline. This research study involved 16 university students to determine the impact of an adapted meditative strategy and relaxation technique that supports the introduction of transcendental meditation as a contemplative practice using a smartphone app. This research was conducted for four weeks among graduates and undergraduates of a university located in the state of Delaware, in the United States. It was identified that classroom discipline improved through the implemented meditation intervention.

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Keywords: self-regulation, academic performance, discipline

Introduction

Schools and colleges increase demands on students' attentiveness and classroom discipline. J. Anderson (2015) offers a good overview of how Educational Psychology Review - an international forum - looked at evidence from 15 peer-reviewed studies examining whether meditation improved students' well-being, social competence, and academic performance. Helping students build resilience and cope with life's challenges as they learn was therefore essential for classroom engagement within a modest period. Most universities have student

engagement programs available to their students such as education, resources (e.g., pamphlets, presentations, workshops), and opportunities to participate in wellness programs (e.g., yoga, meditation, and fitness training) (Reetz et al., 2016). Schools and colleges are now using advanced technologies like mobile apps as modes of delivery for meditative and relaxation techniques as an effective and economic strategy for improving class discipline. This study reports adherence to a consumer-based meditation mobile application and tests its effect on classroom discipline among university students. Meditation takes many forms, such as focused attention (concentration), open monitoring, and non-dual awareness (mindfulness). Concentration-building meditation, also termed focused attention meditation (FAM) practice, has proven to reduce anxiety and create awareness. FAM improves attentiveness, diminishes distractions, builds problem-solving ability, and ultimately leads to the achievement of learning goals when adolescents become aware of their learning potential (Jeon and Cheong, 2018).

Need for the Study

According to Vago and Zeidan (2016), studies that have been conducted on meditative practices are overwhelmingly positive, and science has detected changes in brain waves. Images of the frontal cortex of the brain are different before meditation and after; individuals become more compassionate after meditating (Lim, Condon, & DeSteno, 2015). Meditation techniques can be adapted for adults, children, teens, and those with intellectual disabilities (Chadi et al. 2018; Singh & Hwang, 2020). Literature indicates inadequacy in university-level classroom curriculum for appropriate strategies for meditation and relaxation techniques, and concentration-building exercises as modes of learning engagement. This contributes to the reason why, when it comes to real-life action and social-emotional well-being, we find ourselves so awfully deficient.

This was an explanatory sequential research design framework using mixed method with pre-test and post-test questionnaires to be chosen for data collection and data analysis of gathered data from enrolled students at Delaware State University. Exploring facts to validate the findings and designing an intervention process followed by interpretation of outcome with descriptive analysis of learning experience was the core purpose of the research analysis. The ‘Count Prayers’ mobile app was implemented to help in meditation, and it was believed that using the daily meditation log and graphs inbuilt in the mobile app would help in measuring the potential usage frequency by the students during the 4-week training period. The researcher controlled multiple conditions for intervention manipulation like duration or sequence of mobile app usage, listening to transcendental sound and length of reflective writing. In this case, all participants in the single group participated in the experimental treatment, with each group becoming control of its own.

Meditation delivered via a mobile app was chosen as an appealing and efficacious method to significantly improve class discipline among university students. Smartphones are a critical agent of learning infrastructure in contemporary classrooms. Due to inadequate research findings, there was a lack of proper empirical studies and guidelines for tracking learning perception and class discipline using meditation strategy combined with proper relaxation strategy in education settings. New research was indeed needed to evaluate by correlating the effectiveness of transcendental meditation based on factors such as learning engagement and class discipline among university students.

Background of the Problem

Students with suicidal intention do not seek essential treatment (Pedrelli, Nyer, Yeung, Zulauf & Wilens, 2015), which was worrisome to many in higher education. Timely referral and counselling interventions do not take place until a tragic incident occurs or high rate of attrition

was detected. The institutional challenge of identifying students at risk and providing counseling service on campus remains to support emotional development. Therefore, proper intervention programs to help students improve their classroom discipline and attendance became a priority for universities. “Today’s student deal with cross-cultural issues, family dysfunction, poor frustration tolerance, experimentation with drugs and alcohol, and weak interpersonal attachments” (Kitzrow, 2003), which leads to poor attendance and weak class discipline.

Figure 1

Patterns and Attributes of Key Concepts

Note: The figure depicts patterns and attributes of key concepts derived from student interview.

Materials and Methods

- Participant’s classroom attendance and punctuality in assignment submission was measured collected before and after the 4-week intervention program.
- Participant’s memory score was computed before and after the 4-week intervention, based on ability to respond with numerical answers to a random passage read aloud to determine students’ attention and concentration level.

- The average attendance, punctuality, and concentration level were used to determine class discipline.
- Identified Participant's reflective writing skills for determining students' learning perception before and after the 4-week intervention.
- A 5-minute short meditation audio-visual was played along with visualization by listening to soothing 'sound waves with different frequencies' as a relaxation technique.
- Identified the linkage of duration of meditation practiced to the change in class discipline

Research Results and Findings

Table 1.

Descriptive statistics showing correlation of meditation duration to improvement in attendance.

	Mean	Std. Dev.	N
Meditation Duration	65.63	10	16
Improvement in Attendance	10.5	2.5	16

Correlations

		Meditation Duration	Improvement in Attendance
Meditation Duration	Pearson Correlation	1	0.944**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001
	N	16	16
Improvement in Attendance	Pearson Correlation	0.944**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	
	N	16	16

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

From the quantitative findings, the researcher could identify that transcendental meditation performed (Unit in Minutes) using mobile app intervention over one month had a strong correlation with improvement in classroom attendance.

Figure 2.

Crosstab Query Showing 3 Participants' improvement in Learning Perception

Codes	G	K	T	Total
<input type="radio"/> Improvement	1	2	3	6
<input type="radio"/> Not Improved	0	1	1	2
Total	1	3	4	8

Note: Learning perception was identified for students who practiced more than average duration and from the Figure it could be estimated that participant 'T' had an improved perception compared to Participant 'G' and 'K'.

Table 2.

Descriptive statistics on frequency of meditation duration

Statistics					
Meditation Duration (Min) (Binned)					
N	Valid	16			
	Missing	0			
Mean	3.88				
Std. Deviation	1.784				

Meditation Duration (Min) (Binned)					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20 - 39	7	43.8	43.8	43.8
	60 - 79	1	6.3	6.3	50.0
	80 - 99	4	25.0	25.0	75.0
	100+	4	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	16	100.0	100.0	

Note: This table helped in determining the frequency of duration of meditation practiced. It depicts that 31% of the sample population practiced more than an hour for the training program.

Finally, our results suggest that when university students practiced transcendental meditation their learning perception and concentration level improved. From the qualitative findings, the researcher was able to assert that the quantitative findings were correct from the reflective writing samples of the participants. Participants were able to handle their personal problems better by prioritizing their decisions. Besides, the transcendental meditation practiced in self-paced mode with the meditation app helped the participants develop their imagination and creative ability, and improved clarity of thoughts most economically and efficiently.

Research Summary

This research was conducted among a relatively suburban, homogeneous population. Significantly more research was found to be still needed to examine the effectiveness of meditation strategy with diverse sample populations and in different settings for successful curriculum implementation, and possible concerns or contraindications for its use.

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